

Semantic Data Modeling for the Census Database Deliverable 1 - Base Data Analysis Report

This document consists of the final base data analysis report produced as an outcome of the completion of Work Package 1 (WP1) as defined in the Semantic Data Modelling Proposal of 26/10/2020. It comprised a deep analysis of the extant Census data and its history in order to support the Census project in the dual goals of implementing an upgrade and migration of their data from easydb 4 to easydb 6 (fylr) as well as to ensure that the resultant data model is able to support the project's aim to move into the field of semantic data. Takin.solutions carried out a comprehensive communication with the Census team at the Humboldt University in order to fully understand the data structure, the specificity of the data, and the desired improvements, which will facilitate the Census database's sustainable future. A crucial part was also the continuous communication with the easydb specialists at Programmfabrik to ensure a fluent data migration process with respect to data preservation and expressivity for representation in CIDOC CRM, and in order to prevent any severe technical difficulties associated with the semantically adapted data structure. After the completion of a scheduled pre-migration meeting with the Census team and Programmfabrik, Takin.solutions will be at a position to begin the conceptual modelling of the data.

The report is divided into sections following the existing data structure and logic. Some sections combine the analysis of fields or field types that occur at multiple places across the database. Those are discussed under heading 'General'. The individual models and the necessary adjustments are then described separately. An initial Introduction section brings in the history and the detailed structure of the document.

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	2
2. General	3
2.1. Alias Field	3
2.2. Comment / Notes Fields	5
2.3. Normdaten / Authority List Fields	7
2.4. Dimension	8
2.5. Date References	12
2.6. Other Identifier	16
2.7. Uncertainty with Question Marks	17
3. Model by Model	18
3.1. Monument	18
3.1.1. Monument Condition	18
3.1.2. Creation and Renaissance Date	20

3.1.3. Preservation History Nested Table	21
3.1.4. Provenance History Nested Table	21
3.1.5. Artists Name	22
3.2. Monument Class	24
3.3. Monument Type	24
3.4. Monument Current State	24
3.5. Monument First State	24
3.6. Monument Material	24
3.7. Monument Name Type	25
3.8. Monument Number	25
3.9. Monument Original	25
3.10. Monument Reason	25
3.11. Monument Preservation History Action	25
3.12. Document	26
3.12.1. Date	26
3.12.2. Artists/Author	26
3.12.3. Archetype, Copy and Parallel Copy Nested Tables	26
3.13. Document Inscription Type	26
3.14. Document Inscription Position	27
3.15. Document Medium Visual	27
3.16. Document Medium Written	27
3.17. Document Ordering Note	27
3.18. Document Representation Method	27
3.19. Document Revision	28
3.20. Document Source	28
3.21. Date	28
3.22. Name	28
3.23. Image	28
3.24. Image Location	29
3.25. Image Source	29
3.26. Location	29
3.27. Location Type	30
3.28. Bibliography	30
3.29. Style	30
4. Conclusion	30

1.Introduction

This document forms the recommendations of Takin.solutions to the Census project as it organizes the migration of their data from easydb4 to the latest version of easydb (fyI). The recommendations are made after a series of discussions with Timo Strauch and Kathleen Christian regarding the existing data structure. These discussions provided extensive background information on the original intention and actual use of tables and fields to curate data within the Census project over the past 40 years.

The recommendations below intend to provide suggestions for actionable and reasonable improvements to the data structures implemented in the new version of the Census system of record (easydb 6/fyI). These recommendations are created after considering the original and actual use of fields and taking into account the research aims highlighted as of priority in our dialogue with Prof. Christian and Dr. Strauch. They consider both the intended research and the re-representation requirements in Linked Open Data, adopting especially the CIDOC CRM standard and SARI Reference Data Models perspective.

It is intended that the recommendations are first considered by the Census team (Kathleen Christian) for their feasibility/desirability and then, after approval or disapproval, also considered by the Programmfabrik team in charge of the setup of the new instance of easydb/fyI and the migration of extant data between the two systems.

We have divided the recommendations into two general sections. In the first section, we provide recommendations that apply across data models (fields that are common across data models). In the second section, we provide recommendations per data model. The second section is ordered in the more or less relative importance of models rather than alphabetically. This choice was made since a substantial distinction was noted through our discussions on the data between the significance and focus of data curation regarding primary entities of interest like the Monument and Document as opposed to secondary entities of interest like Name or Location.

For each change that we suggest, we note:

- **Title:** a name for the change (reminiscent of the original field/nested table/model name)
- **Census DB Appearance:** on which models the fields/tables are to be found
- **Description:** what the field/table/model is supposed to enable in terms of documentation and what the issue with it lies
- **Modelling Suggestion:** alternatives for how to remodel from a smaller (minimal) to a larger (maximal) intervention
- **Migration Suggestion:** here we provide relevant suggestions on how the change in migration from a simple 1:1 translation to a more complex transformation might be realized

These solutions are named relative to the typical field display name used in the current implementation of easydb (<https://census6.5.easydb.de/>) for this information.

The final decision on the best solution regarding the project's goals lies with the Census team; the final decision on the best technical implementation of the changes in easydb lies with Programmfabrik. We present the full range of options and attempt to introduce no bias in the final choice.

2. General

In this section, we provide modelling changes for fields that appear across different models in the system.

2.1. Alias Field

Census DB Appearances

- Name
- Location
- Document
- Monument
 - Alias (Link)

Description

This field recurs over multiple models. It is used to identify different, non-preferred names for the object being documented. These should be recorded separately in a single entry for each name. The suggestions for modelling and migration follow.

Modelling Suggestion

- **Minimum**

At base the data in this field is multivalued. It needs to be handled as independent data points and not as separated values in one field. Therefore we recommend making a nested table with the following field:

Nested table 'Alias'		
Field name	Field type	Easydb data type
Alias	String	Single line text

- **Middle**

Different names serve different functions. It is often highly relevant to know the kind of name that is being documented (primary, pseudonym). In this scenario, the nested table would consist of the following:

Nested table 'Alias'		
Field name	Field type	Easydb data type
Alias	String	Single line text
Alias type	Dropdown list	Object type "Alias type"

- **Maximum**

It is often important to know who used a name for an entity and for how long or based on what document we have this name. Therefore:

Nested table 'Alias'		
Field name	Field type	Easydb data type
Alias	String	Single line text
Alias type	Dropdown list	Object type "Alias type"
Start date	Date field for start of use	Date
End date	Date field for end of use	Date
Used by	Reference link	Object type "Name"
Source	Reference link	Object type "Document"

Migration Suggestion

- **Minimum**

Move existing multivalue data into first string field of new multivalue table

- **Medium**

Data currently divided by either semi colons or line returns to be divided into distinct values on the alias nested table

Analysis and discussion

Kathleen Christian recommends **MEDIUM** modelling and **MEDIUM** migration. Following the latest discussion with Programmfabrik, the medium migration scenario was already planned for implementation.

2.2. Comment / Notes Fields

Census DB Appearances

The field name typically appears as 'notes' or 'comment'. Relevant data type is also recorded in other fields as identified in the secondary bullet points below:

- Name
- Bibliography
- Document
 - Document Inscription
 - Watermark
- Monument
 - Monument Later Known Replicas Notes
 - Monument Preservation history
 - Details

Description

This kind of field occurs over multiple models. It is used mostly for inputting various notes. These can be of high value in understanding and interpreting the documented entity. Currently, it is a single value text field. It should enable richer/more accurate documentation than this.

Modelling Suggestions

- **Minimum**

Different notes should be something that can be considered separately. At present, this field combines information from many perspectives over time with no programmatic way to separate it. This information should be treated as distinct units of documentation. Therefore:

Nested table 'Comments'		
Field name	Field type	Easydb data type
Notes	String	Multiline text

- **Medium**

A notes field with no further differentiator lacks data quality for being able to sort internal from external notes, kinds of notes from each other, and the provenance of the note. Specific data regarding the authorship and type of note should be kept, allowing further analysis of this data. Therefore:

Nested table 'Comments'		
Field name	Field type	Easydb data type
Note	String	Multiline text
Note type	Drop down list	Object type "Note type"
Note author	Reference Link	Object type "Name"

NB: the question of the author's record is interesting. At present, it is treated not as a primary entity but just a backend information unit. However, the curator can become a large part of the story.

- **Maximum**

The time when a statement is made is also often valuable. The fact that the Census database is a 40 years digital humanities (DH) project proves this. In this case, one might also want to consider the date of the curatorial information. Therefore, a nested table with the following fields is needed:

Nested table 'Comments'		
Field name	Field type	Easydb data type
Note	String	Multiline text
Note type	Drop down list	Object type "Note type"
Note author	Reference Link	Object type "Name"
Note date early	Date	Date*
Note date late	Date	Date*
* if cs_date table is to be kept as it is then data type should be 'object type "Date"'		

NB: how the date is represented is dependent on how the Census team ultimately decides it wants to implement temporal information (based on the current 'date' central table or using new approaches. See this issue below.

Migration Suggestion

The data in these fields is very rich and is a high priority for saving. That being said, the field until now has had no structural richness. It would be nearly impossible / curatorially unwise to automatically split this data because of how it was inputted. It could be transferred to the new nested table's first content field, and a future project could look at the value of separating this information. The new data model will however, allow for better / more accurate data entry in the future.

Analysis and discussion

Kathleen Christian recommends **MAXIMUM** modelling. The creation of new fields here is essential but has no immediate impact on data migration and could be achieved at a later stage, followed by the separation of meaningful data into categories, while keeping the current *status quo* into a verbatim field for reference.

2.3. Normdaten / Authority List Fields

Census Database Appearance

This data appears with various names in various nested tables. The following is a summary of the ones we have identified

- Name
 - GND
 - ULAN
 - VIAF
- Location
 - Geonames
 - GND
 - idai.gazetteer
 - Pleiades
 - TGN
 - VIAF

Description

Sets of fields are found across multiple models that enable linking a resource to an authority record, which is also a document for this entity. This set of fields have been built as separate structures for each authority referred to. While this manner of modelling the data cleanly indicates the possible authorities for each entity type (one knows what data to fill in), this manner of modelling is not easily extendable and makes searching more difficult.

Modelling Suggestion

We recommend making a single Authority Reference Nested Table style which allows a number of entries from different resources and reuse this nested table style across all models for which *normdaten* is entered.

Nested table 'Authority lists'		
Field name	Field type	Easydb data type
Authority	Drop down list	Object type "Authority list type"
URL	url	Weblink

Migration Suggestion

Since this generally follows the existing structure, the migration should not be that complicated. The authority list should be populated with the extant list of authorities (see list above), and when data is moved from one of the existing separate structures (the URL) the appropriate authority should be appended to the authority field.

Analysis and discussion

Kathleen Christian accepts the collection of all authority sources/*normdaten* into the proposed nested table. Although we had a discussion about this with Programmfabrik, it seems like the *normdaten* in their current stage exist in separate nested tables. This could be for migration purposes but needs to be discussed further.

2.4. URL Nested Tables

The URL nested table pattern is a good idea. You can store many different URLs and associate a human readable label to them. This should be kept separate from the *normdaten* information.

Analysis and discussion

Programmfabrik has already created a nested table for supposedly this purpose called 'Authority data Type', which contains three fields: *normdaten* (single line text), url (single line text), and remark (multiline text). We would advise to change the data type of *normdaten* to object type containing a standardised list of resources and the url from single text to weblink.

This table seems to be more appropriate for *normdaten* specifically and needs to be further discussed. There is a separate URL table, which contains currently title and note fields. It is possible both are intended for this specific use (*normdaten* vs. URL), the only question remains with the gnd, geonames, etc. nested tables.

2.4. Dimension

Census Database Appearance

The field name appears as 'Dimension' in the following two tables:

- Monument
- Document

Description

This field is used to record the physical dimensions of documents or monuments. It is presently entered as a single text string.

Modelling Suggestion

Dimension data can be of high value for research when it is split into its component elements. As a single text string it has less value.

- **Minimum**

This is a minimum because it allows to follow current practice (just a text field, but also opens the way for a more granular practice):

Nested table 'Dimension'		
Field name	Field type	Easydb data type
Measurement Verbatim	String (here goes the measurement as one finds it currently in documentation)	Single line text
Measurement Value	String (here we put the value, ideally a single integer but if necessary a combination of values)	Number/Decimal
Measurement Unit	dropdown list (a list of measurement types like cm, inch)	Object type 'Measurement Unit'
Measurement Type	dropdown list (a list of measurement types like height, width, area)	Object type 'Measurement Type'
Measurement Comment	String (additional information like 'without base')	Multiline text

Here the idea is to have a nested table to allow the capture of more than one dimension and its details (the value vs. the measurement unit vs. the kind of thing measured). NB: This allows for alignment with CIDOC CRM, which strictly requires only one integer per dimension. So, if you measure height and width, they should be in separate places. Here we accept areas (HxW) as one value, the type of measure being area.

- **Medium**

This is medium because it includes another field that allows the sourcing of the measurement. This is often important when dimensions change over time but it may be out of Census scope.

Nested table 'Dimension'		
Field name	Field type	Easydb data type
Measurement Verbatim	String (here goes the measurement as one finds it currently in documentation)	Single line text
Measurement Value	String (here we put the value, ideally a single integer but if necessary a combination of values)	Single line text
Measurement Unit	dropdown list (a list of measurement types like cm, inch)	Object type 'Measurement Unit'

Measurement Type	dropdown list (a list of measurement types like height, width, area)	Object type 'Measurement Type'
Measurement Comment	String (additional information like 'without base')	Multiline text
Measurement Source	resource link (to the bibliography or document resource type)	Object type 'Document'

- **Maximum**

This is maximum because it insists on having one integer per dimension. This means areas could not be recorded in one dimension. Instead you would have to create a height and width dimension, for example.

Nested table 'Dimension'		
Field name	Field type	Easydb data type
Measurement Verbatim	String (here goes the measurement as one finds it currently in documentation)	Single line text
Measurement Value	Integer (here we put only a single real value integer, so measurements of area must be recorded in separate entries one for height and one for width)	Number/Decimal
Measurement Unit	dropdown list (a list of measurement types like cm, inch)	Object type 'Measurement Unit'
Measurement Type	dropdown list (a list of measurement types like height, width, NOT area)	Object type 'Measurement Type'
Measurement Comment	String (additional information like 'without base')	Multiline text
Measurement Source	Resource link (to the bibliography or document resource type)	Object type 'Document'

Migration Suggestion

Currently dimension data is kept in one text field. This may be difficult to parse into multiple fields.

- **Minimum**

Just put existing data into first verbatim field of the new suggested nested table

- **Medium**

If all dimensions are just area, then can also put dimension information in the 'value' field and add a type 'area' to the measurement type and possibly a unit to the dimension unit.

- **Maximum**

Divide the measurement information into its smallest units and have multiple values in the new dimension nested table.

Overall, it is most likely to proceed with the minimum migration suggestion given the potential lack of standardization of the measurement field. There are some well-structured records, but many are not. The ideal result would require a data cleaning project.

Analysis and discussion

Kathleen Christian recommends following the **MINIMUM** modelling approach but having a couple of features from the other two proposed scenarios, such as selecting integer as a mandatory Measurement value, and NOT allowing area to be added in Measurement type; instead add 2 sets of measurements that can be used to calculate the area. Therefore, we propose a new **MINIMUM2** modelling table:

Nested table 'Dimension'		
Field name	Field type	Easydb data type
Measurement Verbatim	String (here goes the measurement as one finds it currently in documentation)	Single line text
Measurement Value	Integer (here we put only a single real value integer, so measurements of area must be recorded in separate entries one for height and one for width)	Number/Decimal
Measurement Unit	dropdown list (a list of measurement types like cm, inch)	Object type 'Measurement Unit'
Measurement Type	dropdown list (a list of measurement types like height, width, NOT area)	Object type 'Measurement Type'

Measurement Comment	String (additional information like 'without base')	Multiline text
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The migration policy for now has been advised to place the contents of the current measurements field into the Measurement Verbatim field (**MINIMUM** migration) and at a later stage reorganise and clean the data so it matches the appropriate fields, while keeping the old verbatim for reference.

2.5. Date References

Census Database Appearance

- Name
 - Birth -> usually only relevant to the individual CRM E67 Birth
 - Death -> usually only relevant to the individual CRM E69 Death
- Document
 - Date -> creation
- Style
 - Begin -> temporal ordering; style is actually a period, which 'starts after or with'
 - End -> temporal ordering; style is actually a period, which 'ends with'
- Monument
 - Renaissance dating -> holds contradicting dating of the monument -> the renaissance point of view
 - Creation date -> E12 Production, (such information is usually documented just of the individual monument on the monument record, not separate to it as an event record in its own right)
 - Preservation history -> E11 Modification, multivalued, this information could be kept on a separate event record just in case you wanted to document preservation acts in their own right. However, given the focus of documentation retaining this even information as a multivalued nested table on the monument record itself makes sense.
 - Provenance history -> E8 Acquisition (maybe), multivalued, again, this information could be kept on a separate event record just in case you wanted to document preservation acts in their own right. However, given the focus of documentation retaining this even information as a multivalued nested table on the monument record itself makes sense. we want to document the individual acts

Description

On many tables there is a reference to the 'date' table. The date table is both a benefit and a problem in terms of Census data management. It is excellent that dates have been given a top priority and are documented in their own sense. It creates some difficulties because the date table mixes the category of 'period/event/activity' in the sense of an on-going cultural activity that took place at some time, some place, with some people involved and the notion of date, where we mean the pure temporal information (the random time slice of 'October 1, 258' for example). In terms of semantic representation of data (especially using the CIDOC

CRM) this is a fundamental distinction to be made, and is not clearly done in the present representation of the data).

The basic problem here is that the date table documents two types of things (i.e. having a table for documenting both people and soil samples, where the entities are so different that one really needs different data structures to capture the essence of the data and to allow for data representation). The present date table forces the documentation of temporal events and of time spans to be done with the same tool. This means that the following entities have the same importance:

'The reign of Tiberius'

'1 May 353'

'2 September 557 - 6 January 1012'

In our expert opinion, this is not a good data practice. While the reign of Tiberius is a period in the proper sense, (well known historical event by which something can be dated or otherwise associated with) the single day of '1 May 353' and the 'range' '2 September 557 - 6 January 1012' are random time slices that appertain to individual events that are relative to an individual entity (its creation, its preservation, its destruction). Only by accident do two entities share the same date not because of some essential ontological connection between them that must be documented.

Thus, while the date table is a good table to have, it would ideally document only cultural or historical periods (such as a reign, a pontificate, the European Bronze Age, 16th century Renaissance Europe) and the pure date information would be migrated on to the entities to which they pertain regarding the events for which they provide the temporal information.

Modelling Suggestions

- **Minimum**

Change nothing. Semantically, it makes the data a bit difficult to work with because events and their times are merged. Also there are instances of 'event' or 'period' that are arbitrary (also not a very good data management practice), e.g.: timespans. It will create less clean data as the events are arbitrary, but it can be more or less usable.

This is a status quo decision. From an accuracy of data point of view, it is the least desirable option but from the change difficulty for migration most manageable. In this circumstance, semantic data can still be produced but it is less accurate and therefore less sustainable.

- **Maximum**

For each reference to 'date' from another model, do the following:

Nested table 'Event'		
Field name	Field type	Easydb data type
Nested table 'Action Type'		
Event Type	Dropdown List	Object type 'Action type'
Sub - Nested table 'TimeSpan'		
Verbatim Date	string	Single line text
Earliest Date	Date/calendar	Date
Latest Date	Date/calendar	Date
Falls within Period	resource link	Object type 'Date'
Attribution	Drop down list (contemporary/renaissance)	Object type 'Attribution type'
Sub - Nested table 'Actors Involved'		
Actor	resource link	Object type 'Name'
Actor Role	Drop down list	Object type 'Actor Role'
Attribution	Drop down list (contemporary/renaissance)	Object type 'Attribution type'
Sub - Nested table 'Location'		
Location	resource link	Object type 'Location'
Attribution	Drop down list (contemporary/renaissance)	Object type 'Attribution type'

NB: one could do even more complicated modelling of attribution (who thought of this date and when) but from our discussions this does not seem to be a priority at this moment so it is not further presented here).

Migration Suggestion

In the migration, three scenarios come up based on the modelling choice

- **Minimal**

No change, data stays where it is.

- **Maximum**

- **Basic**

The new data structure is created so that on the models, people can now add data for dates within the models that they are working on (i.e., enter the birthday dates on the person/name model in the appropriate nested table. If, in case, the dates are unknown but a period can be referenced, one should use the 'falls within' reference field). In this case, the current date field information is left unchanged and the link to date is just moved to the new field 'falls within'.

Problem: the dates table is filled with random 'date' entities that refer to arbitrary time slices and there will be two different places where this information is kept.

- **Advanced**

The new nested table structures have the same field structure as the dates' entries in the date table. So, in principle, we could use the following to distinguish which entries in the date table are periods and which are dates.

Dates

- Century
- Day
- Month
- Date Range

Periods

- Everything else

NB: If a date record is DATES (century, day, month, or date range) then the value of it should be transported into the first entry of the nested table of the associated record in the new date branch format.

If a date record is PERIODS (anything else) then we simply move the link to the 'falls within' field on the new data structure. (see simple migration solution)

The new protocol for data entry becomes: if this event is century, day, month, or date range then enter the information on the object you are documenting. This information is pertinent/proper to the entity you are documenting and NOT to all/any entity. If you only know a period, use the link to the dates table (which becomes a 'period' table).

Analysis and discussion

Kathleen Christian agrees with the proposed structural change as described in the **MAXIMUM** scenario, which will result in creating a new table, repurposing the current Date table but turning it into a Period table. The Period will have 'date from' and 'date to' fields defining the period per se, while all other dates will be incorporated into the appropriate tables (i.e. birthdate and death date will be fields bearing calendar dates in the Name/Person table). This adaptation needs to be further discussed with Programmfabrik since it requires a more complex migration workflow.

2.6. Other Identifier

The field name appears as an inventory of a sort (see below).

Census DB Appearance

- Image
 - Negative_ID
- Monument
 - Inventory No
 - Later Known Replicas -> Inventory

Description

This appears on the monument table. Having a specific table for holding many identifiers could be long run helpful (they tend to get more than one).

Minimum

Many identifiers can be applied to the same object over time. These identifiers can be crucial for finding an object in the database. The potential number of identifiers of interest is infinite. Therefore:

Nested table 'Identifiers'		
Field name	Field type	Easydb data type
Identifier content	String	Single line text
Identifier type	Drop down list	Object type 'Identifier type'

Here we enable both entering as separate units of information as many identifiers as necessary but also indicate what kind of identifier is given.

Maximum

It is often important to know not just an identifier but whom it was assigned by and how we know that this identifier pertains to the object of interest. Therefore:

Nested table 'Identifiers'		
Field name	Field type	Easydb data type
Identifier content	String	Single line text
Identifier type	Drop down list	Object type 'Identifier type'
Identifier used by	Resource link	Object type 'Name'
Identifier source	Resource link	Object type 'Document'

Migration Suggestion

Take existing data and put it in the first content field of the new nested table

Analysis and discussion

Kathleen Christian recommends to follow the **MAXIMUM** modelling scenario. There is no impact on the data migration, only a nested table instead of a single field required. The suggested additional fields are for future use and can be implemented at a later stage.

2.7. Uncertainty with Question Marks

Type lists with uncertainty

Monument_class
Monument_type
Monument_original
Monument_first_state
Monument_material
monument_reason

It is best not to express uncertainty in type lists by making a type that is the type plus the character for a question mark. It is recommended to create a second field which qualifies the first field and which can also be a controlled list. It can be populated with a term like 'uncertain'.

Wherever there is a reference to a type field and there is uncertainty associated in the type field itself, create a nested table and add a second controlled field to indicate uncertainty.

Analysis and discussion

Kathleen Christian recommends creating a new nested table accommodating uncertainty, to be applied where appropriate (see 'type lists with uncertainty' above):

Nested table 'Uncertainty'		
Field name	Field type	Easydb data type
Uncertainty	Boolean	Single line text
Uncertainty note	String	Multiline text
Uncertainty Attributed By	Resource link	Object type 'Name'

Migration Suggestion

Simply move the data as is to the new nested table in the 'Uncertainty note' field. A later cleanup project could find all instances with a question mark and add the uncertainty value to its partner boolean field. Potential uncertainty attribution field has also been proposed.

3. Model by Model

3.1. Monument

3.1.1. Monument Condition

Census Database Appearance

- Monument

Description

This field exists in 'monument', there is a 'first state' and then a 'current state' set of nested tables. This is not a very good structure since 'current' very soon is not going to be current, and 'first' is imprecise. We recommend a nested table for documenting states and their times.

The epistemic value of this field is to provide a 'witness' to the monument. Currently only two witnesses are allowed - the first renaissance witness and the last contemporary witness.

This is a deficient documentation practice because it is unlikely we can ever know with certainty when the first renaissance witness was (what happens if we find an earlier one) and the present, unfortunately, keeps falling behind us. The Census database which has a forty year history is a practical reminder of this. Therefore, it would be best to be able to track condition information for what it is, a temporally bound witness of a state of a thing. First and last should be decided by what is known in the database. Find an earlier witness, then this is the earliest witness. Have a new state for the monument in the present? Then this is the latest condition.

Modelling Suggestions

- **Minimal**

Condition information is condition information regardless of whether it is in the past or the present. So it should not be kept in separate fields. Therefore:

Nested table 'Monument Condition'		
Field name	Field type	Easydb data type
State type	Drop down list	Object type 'State type'
State moment	Drop down list ("Original", "Present")	Object type 'Identifier type'
Source	Resource link	Object type 'Document'

This replicates the current modelling but at least merges the data into one table instead of multiple tables about the same information.

- **Medium**

Condition information is usually only interesting and relevant as a historical witness of a monument in some state at some time. It would be ideal to include temporal information to give this witness value. Therefore:

Nested table 'Monument Condition'		
Field name	Field type	Easydb data type
State type	Drop down list	Object type 'State type'
Earliest Date	Date	Date
Latest Date	Date	Date
Falls within	Resource link	Object type 'Date' ('Period')
Source	Resource link	Object type 'Document'

- **Maximum**

Condition information is a witness of a thing at some time in some state, usually be someone. Therefore:

Nested table 'Monument Condition'		
Field name	Field type	Easydb data type
State type	Drop down list	Object type 'State type'
Earliest Date	Date	Date
Latest Date	Date	Date
Falls within	Resource link	Object type 'Date' ('Period')
Sub - Nested table 'Actors Involved'		
Actor	resource link	Object type 'Name'
Actor Role	Drop down list	Object type 'Actor Role'
Sub - Nested table 'Sources'		
Source	Resource link	Object type 'Document'

Migration Suggestion

The current state nested data is simply in two separate single value nested tables, so it can be moved over to the simpler or less simple models.

Analysis and discussion

Kathleen Christian suggests the **MAXIMUM** modelling scenario adding another level of information to the document condition documentation. The migration needs to be discussed with Programmfabrik.

3.1.2. Creation and Renaissance Date

There are two different nested table sets of fields for linking to date to describe the creation date of the monument. In fact, these are two opinions on the creation date. It would be better to make one nested table called 'creation date', which uses the format recommended in the general recommendations above. Then, it is recommended to put both conflicting opinions in this table, one with the type 'renaissance date' and one with 'present opinion.' Likewise, since there is a creation event nested table, there should be a destruction event nested table as well.

See nested tables:

cs_monument > monument_creation_date_555 and cs_monument > renaissance_date_724

Here are two illustrations of the suggested tables according to the general modelling suggestion for dates above:

Creation Event:

Nested table 'Creation Event'		
Field name	Field type	Easydb data type
Creation Event Name	String	Single line text
Creation Event Type	Drop down list	Object type 'Event Type'
Creation Attributed By	Resource Link	Object type 'Name'
Sub - Nested table 'Actors Involved'		
Actor	resource link	Object type 'Name'
Actor Role	Drop down list	Object type 'Actor Role'
Event Earliest Date	Date	Date
Event Latest Date	Date	Date
Date Type	Drop down list	Object type 'Date Type'
Event Falls Within	Resource Link	Object type 'Date/Period'

Destruction Event:

Nested table 'Destruction Event'		
Field name	Field type	Easydb data type
Destruction Event Name	String	Single line text
Destruction Event Type	Drop down list	Object type 'Event Type'
Destruction Attributed By	Resource Link	Object type 'Name'
Sub - Nested table 'Actors Involved'		
Actor	resource link	Object type 'Name'
Actor Role	Drop down list	Object type 'Actor Role'
Event Earliest Date	Date	Date
Event Latest Date	Date	Date
Date Type	Drop down list	Object type 'Date Type'
Event Falls Within	Resource Link	Object type 'Date/Period'

Analysis and discussion

Kathleen Christian agrees with the above suggestion. Adding dates and attribution to the 'present' opinion will facilitate the sustainable recording of data in the future.

3.1.3. Preservation History Nested Table

This is the documentation of a series of events, activities that led to some modification of the monument and it is a good nested table. Data would be improved if the structure of this table follows the general recommendations for a 'date reference' as listed in the general recommendations section.

Furthermore, one of the types of 'preservation' is 'destruction'. This should be documented in a separated event nested table 'destruction' parallel to the 'creation' nested table that we suggest for creation date. The date could move here in the present migration but be cleaned up in a later campaign. Destruction should be documented separately from preservation, ontologically representing two contradictory event types.

The type list used here: monument_preservation_history__action should be standardized but this can be done at a later stage systematically in a cleanup project.

Analysis and discussion

Kathleen Christian agrees with the above suggestion. The crucial part in this adaptation is to isolate 'destruction' from preservation and create a new nested table for it.

3.1.4. Provenance History Nested Table

This is the documentation of a series of different kinds of events. We recommend adding at least a type field to indicate whether the provenance event relates to change of custody, change of ownership, or change of location. Furthermore, it would be beneficial to use the general fields suggested for any event reference discussed in the general modelling recommendations.

Analysis and discussion

Kathleen Christian agrees with the above suggestion. Following the discussion we suggest the following nested table:

Nested table 'Provenance History'		
Field name	Field type	Easydb data type
Provenance Event Name	String	Single line text
Provenance Event Type	Drop down list	Object type 'Event Type'
Provenance Attribute By	Resource Link	Object type 'Name'
Event Earliest Date	Date	Date
Event Latest Date	Date	Date

Event Falls Within	Resource Link	Object type 'Date/Period'
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3.1.5. Artists Name

The artist is the person who was involved in the creation event of the monument as the person who was essential to it coming to be. This should therefore be documented together with the creation information, i.e. the date. So the link to the artist record should be moved into the creation event nested table that would be created if the new method of representing dates suggested in the overall recommendations above is adopted.

Sub issue: there can be three kinds of relation between the artist and the monument as indicated by monument_name_type dropdown. This has implications on where the data should be migrated.

If the value is 'creation artist' then it should land in the nested table for 'creation date' together with the creation date reference. If 'renaissance artist' then together with the 'renaissance' date.

Analysis and discussion

Kathleen Christian agrees overall with the suggestion. After a detailed discussion we are proposing three new nested tables covering the two main event types - 'creation event' and 'destruction event'.

3.2. Monument Class

This reference list is good. Gives a general classification of the kind of monument/artwork. It is also useful for sorting data. We recommend eventually matching it to AAT or other authority and to separate uncertainty into a separate field. See general recommendations above.

Analysis and discussion

Kathleen Christian agrees with the suggestion for adding AAT and handling uncertainty as described in the uncertainty section.

3.3. Monument Type

This reference list is good. It gives a classification of the artwork/monument by form/function. It is also a good candidate for matching to AAT or other vocabularies at a later stage.

Analysis and discussion

Kathleen Christian agrees with the suggestion for adding AAT classification. Future separation between form and function in two separate nested tables is highly recommended.

3.4. Monument Current State

This reference list should be merged with 'monument first state', since a state is a state. Uncertainty should be moved out into a separate field, see overall recommendation on uncertainty and question marks. 'Unknown' is generally not a good type either. If absolutely

necessary, it should be placed into a note field in the related nested table. See the above recommendation on merging 'current' and 'original' state nested tables into one.

Analysis and discussion

Kathleen Christian agrees with the proposed suggestion. See the comments above.

3.5. Monument First State

See monument current state.

3.6. Monument Material

This reference list is alright. Good candidate for eventual matching to AAT. It is recommended to consider adding a broader/narrow term field (pointing back to the same table), to allow building hierarchy without using 'name + :'.

See general uncertainty comments.

Analysis and discussion

Kathleen Christian agrees with the suggestion for adding AAT and handling uncertainty as described in the uncertainty section.

3.7. Monument Name Type

This is a functional dropdown list for characterizing how an artist is related to the monument. See recommendation on different models for moving the actor information.

Analysis and discussion

Kathleen Christian agrees with the overall suggestion.

3.8. Monument Number

This table is unnecessary. The information in it is useful as it indicates how many copies of a monument there are but this can be handled by an integer field created directly on the monument model. There is no significance in having a table to represent natural numbers!

Analysis and discussion

Kathleen Christian agrees with the overall suggestion. Table to be reduced to a single field.

3.9. Monument Original

This table is not particularly good. It would be better to replace this with a nested table within the monument model, where one can indicate using an enum list 'yes/no/unknown' and then have another field with a drop down list for uncertainty. See general comments above on uncertainty.

Analysis and discussion

Kathleen Christian agrees with the overall suggestion. Add attribution field to the nested table, indicating who claimed that this is the original.

3.10. Monument Reason

This table is not well named but otherwise is fine. "Cause of Observation" may be a better name? 'Monument reason' suggests that we find here the cause of the monument itself. See comments on uncertainty for cleanup.

Analysis and Discussions

Rename the field to 'cause of observation'.

3.11. Monument Preservation History Action

This list is fine and could be aligned to AAT. It is recommended not to put uncertainty in the list. 'Destroyed' is not a preservation action and should be isolated and associated with a destruction event. Document this in a dedicated destruction nested table for documenting the end of life of a monument. See the recommendation on documenting state in the monument table.

Analysis and discussion

Kathleen Christian agrees with the suggestion for adding AAT and uncertainty as described in the uncertainty section. As a part of data cleaning activities in the future, 'destroyed' should be removed from this list. It will be a part of a designated destruction event nested table.

3.12. Document

3.12.1. Date

This should become a nested table for describing the specific creation information of this object if you follow the general advice on reconfiguring date recording. The new nested table allows all attributes related to the creation of the document to be recorded. Since the destruction might also be interesting, this too should be recorded in a separate table.

Here are two illustrations of the suggested tables according to the general modelling suggestion for dates above:

Creation Event:

Nested table 'Creation Event'		
Field name	Field type	Easydb data type
Creation Event Name	String	Single line text
Creation Event Type	Drop down list	Object type 'Event Type'
Creation Attributed By	Resource Link	Object type 'Name'
Sub - Nested table 'Actors Involved'		
Actor	resource link	Object type 'Name'

Actor Role	Drop down list	Object type 'Actor Role'
Event Earliest Date	Date	Date
Event Latest Date	Date	Date
Date Type	Drop down list	Object type 'Date Type'
Event Falls Within	Resource Link	Object type 'Date/Period'

Destruction Event:

Nested table 'Destruction Event'		
Field name	Field type	Easydb data type
Destruction Event Name	String	Single line text
Destruction Event Type	Drop down list	Object type 'Event Type'
Destruction Attributed By	Resource Link	Object type 'Name'
Sub - Nested table 'Actors Involved'		
Actor	resource link	Object type 'Name'
Actor Role	Drop down list	Object type 'Actor Role'
Event Earliest Date	Date	Date
Event Latest Date	Date	Date
Date Type	Drop down list	Object type 'Date Type'
Event Falls Within	Resource Link	Object type 'Date/Period'

Analysis and discussion

Kathleen Christian agrees with the suggestion.

3.12.2. Artists/Author

If you follow the general advice for reconfiguring date information and create a nested table for the creation event on the document model, then the artist information should move from here into that nested table.

Analysis and discussion

Kathleen Christian agrees with the suggestion.

3.12.3. Archetype, Copy and Parallel Copy Nested Tables

These are related nested tables for documenting the 'copy' relation between documents. If 'archetype' is filled out, then it indicates the copies of the document you are presently

describing. If 'copy' is filled out, it indicates the archetype document that the document presently being described is a copy of. If 'parallel copy' is filled out, then it indicates that the related document is also a copy of another unknown document of which the document presently being described is also a copy.

This system works well enough. However, there is a chance for the data to go out of sync in the case of archetype and copy, since one needs to duplicate the information in two places. If possible, create a data structure which automatically documents the inverse link. No solid proposal here since we are not sure how this might be technically achieved in easydb, typically a join table.

Analysis and discussion

Kathleen Christian agrees with the overall suggestion, technicalities to be discussed..

3.13. Document Inscription Type

This table contains values that cover the meaning of the text, the style of the text, the physical look of the text, the language of the text, the kind of image, commentary, assessments of the legibility and other information. It should be the focus of a further data analysis and creation of separate fields for separate kinds of information: e.g.: the list suggested above. This is not likely a priority at the moment but would significantly improve the value of this information once sorted.

Analysis and discussion

Kathleen Christian agrees with the suggestion. New fields for future use and data cleanup at a later stage predicted.

3.14. Document Inscription Position

This does not really need to be a lookup table the way that it is presently done. It is simply a description. It would be better if this is the documentation strategy, to make it a notes field. (see general comments on notes above). Alternatively, decide on a limited list of normalized terms which would stay here and add a note field (so you would have a nested table with the 'position' and a 'note on the position' where the documentalist can write additional information that is not normalized.)

Consider putting in a IIIF or other annotation tool.

Analysis and discussion

Kathleen Christian agrees with the suggestion including the incorporation of a IIIF tool.

3.15. Document Medium Visual

This is a reasonable and well controlled list. It could be a candidate for matching to AAT or similar. Consider creating a hierarchy relation on this table in order to be able to link a higher to a lower term in the data structure rather than through the labelling of the terms.

Analysis and discussion

Kathleen Christian agrees with the suggestion for adding AAT.

3.16. Document Medium Written

These values are well controlled however the information could and probably should be split between form and function e.g.: book, chapter, page vs. romance, topography, etc.

Analysis and discussion

Kathleen Christian agrees with the suggestion for adding AAT. Separate form from function in the future.

3.17. Document Ordering Note

This is used to create the hierarchy of the functional relation of parts of the document. Book -> Page, Poem -> Verse. It would be good to enable a hierarchy amongst the terms. Needs data cleanup.

Analysis and Discussion

Rename it to 'Document Form'.

3.18. Document Representation Method

This is a reasonable list. Could be matched to AAT in future. The terms 'unknown' and 'copy' are dubious (as they are not representation methods).

3.19. Document Revision

Only three entries. This is not a useful field. Should be put as a statement about the object. Can be deleted manually after migration.

3.20. Document Source

This table represents the initial contributing projects. Maybe it would be better to call this 'contributing projects' table? This way you could keep further information about the projects. Regardless, as a reference it can be useful to know from whence the first record of an object came for accounting and accountability purposes. Consider extending this to all records.

3.21. Date

This table plays a central role in the data model of the Census. Since the effects of changing it (which we strongly recommend to do) are relevant to almost all models, we have commented on the proposed changes in the general analysis section above.

'Date from' and 'date to' fields: change data type to date. If necessary move existing data (if poorly formatted) to a string text as 'verbatim' date.

Analysis and discussion

Kathleen Christian agrees with the overall change in the model in respect to Date (see above).

3.22. Name

This table represents individual people. Normally this could then be called a 'person' table which would be less confusing than name, which sounds like a table for appellations.

Key changes that we would recommend consider the documentation of the birth and death of the individual. We cover our recommendation for this question under the general 'dates' modelling suggestions above. However, do note that if it is decided to move to recording the dates of the birth and death directly on the person model as per our suggestion, as well as common additional information like people involved and location, then it is the case that in the migration the location reference field for birth (birthplace) and death (place_of_death) should be migrated to the new nested table for birth and death under the appropriate location reference node.

Here are two illustrations of the suggested tables according to the general modelling suggestion for dates above:

Birth Event:

Nested table 'Birth Event'		
Field name	Field type	Easydb data type
Birth Event Name	String	Single line text
Birth Attributed By	Resource Link	Object type 'Name'
Sub - Nested table 'Actors Involved'		
Actor	resource link	Object type 'Name'
Actor Role	Drop down list	Object type 'Actor Role'
Event Earliest Date	Date	Date
Event Latest Date	Date	Date
Date Type	Drop down list	Object type 'Date Type'
Event Falls Within	Resource Link	Object type 'Date/Period'

Death Event:

Nested table 'Death Event'		
Field name	Field type	Easydb data type
Death Event Name	String	Single line text
Destruction Attributed By	Resource Link	Object type 'Name'
Sub - Nested table 'Actors Involved'		

Actor	resource link	Object type 'Name'
Actor Role	Drop down list	Object type 'Actor Role'
Event Earliest Date	Date	Date
Event Latest Date	Date	Date
Date Type	Drop down list	Object type 'Date Type'
Event Falls Within	Resource Link	Object type 'Date/Period'

Analysis and discussion

Kathleen Christian agrees with changing the name of this table 'Name' to 'Person' and following the recommendations concerning dates.

3.23. Image

No direct changes to the 'image' table required.

3.24. Image Location

For this table, we would recommend adding a hierarchy field so that you could build the hierarchy of records (rather than doing this via a naming convention). Eventually, one could organize a collaboration with the providing institutions in order to get their official identifiers for the collections data that is referenced. This would support largely the linked data integration process.

As usual this list has some elements in it which do not belong. Things like 'BBB', and 'unknown', which are not locations as well as 'external link', which is also not a location.

Analysis and discussion

Kathleen Christian agrees with the overall suggestions. Tracking image location history is considered important. Enable changes to allow more detailed recording.

3.25. Image Source

This list is largely mixed, involving references to publications, internet sources, dates, institutions, collections, etc. However, in discussion with the Census, it has been understood that it is not a priority field for documentation and there is no strong emphasis on this part of the documentation. Therefore, we recommend no change.

3.26. Copyright

No change.

Analysis and discussion

Kathleen Christian suggests we develop a copyright model and add it to the overall structure, including copyright attribution fields, timespan, etc.

3.26. Location

This table describes locations (qua place) at which things can be found/put/located. This table works well as is. One small reservation comes with the fields buildings and collections. While a building is a location and this is fine, semantically a collection is not a place. A collection is not in its essence somewhere things are but rather a social historical grouping of things. It is not a good idea to document collections in the same table as locations. Collections would deserve their own table (a collection can change place, a collection can be owned, a collection can have artworks as members - all things that locations cannot do).

NB: there is a nested table for linking to the "Name" (i.e.: person) table which had the intention to document 'owners' of locations. Discussion on this field indicates that this function is not often used and the field will likely be deleted. If so, no further discussion needed. Semantically, it doesn't make sense to link a person to a location with no further data. If the field were retained it should be discussed for remodelling.

Analysis and discussion

We need to reconsider this table once again in order to establish how feasible it is to separate buildings from collections. It is important for research as well as ontologically to treat collections as such and associate them with buildings and locations.

3.27. Location Type

This table's values are good. Consider aligning to a standard vocab like AAT.

3.28. Bibliography

This table could be improved but given that it is not a focus of the documentation as such, and the Census is satisfied with current practice, no urgent change is necessary.

Analysis and discussion

It is suggested to reference this table to external resources (Getty, for example). Further discussion with Programmfabrik is necessary to define how to automate the population

3.29. Style

Style as documented is strongly related to the 'date' table. Presently, it expresses the 'begin' and 'end' of a style relative to a 'date'. If this means temporal ordering, like 'the Augustan period' started 'the August style' and the 'Tiberian period' ended 'the Augustan style', this is great. If it means that this is a place to put an actual date, like 1/10/254-10/10/367 then it is required to create actual 'from' and 'to' date fields with a date type on the style table.

Analysis and discussion

Potentially move to the 'period' table. Data cleaning might be necessary.

4. Conclusion

This document has offered a series of suggestions for potential changes to the implementation of the Census data model in light of the migration of data from easydb4 to fylr and the potential for updating the way fields have been implemented and data curated at this stage.

The changes have been suggested under the general aim of helping set up a long-term sustainable, flexible and accurate data documentation structure relative to the Census project's goals. The recommendations are made based on previous experience with similar data modelling problems in the cultural heritage domain and bearing in mind the aim of Census to semantically represent its data in a manner compatible with sister projects employing the CIDOC CRM standard and the Swiss Art Research Infrastructure standard reference data models.

The recommendations were broken into general and model-specific suggestions. General recommendations pertained to repeating data patterns found across models for which a different data model implementation could be suggested to support more accurate and flexible documentation. In these cases, if a change is implemented on one model, it would be logical and coherent to change it at all places that it occurs in different models across the Census database. Model-specific recommendations were also made in the case when fields or tables deployed only within the context of a single model required potential changes.

The recommendation was to suggest from minimal to maximal change paths for the model itself and relevant parallel ideas for effectuating a change in the migration path from easydb4 to fylr where the shift in modelling would result in a changed final data structure.

These recommendations have been discussed with the Census and a decision was made on the most suitable case scenario for each model, table and field of concern (minimal, medium or maximum change paths) with respect to their usefulness and priority for supporting ongoing and future research. The preliminary report has been delivered also to Programmfabrik and it is up for discussion concerning data migration difficulties and options. With the completion of WP1 and this final report, we opt to facilitate the data migration process with respect to a sustainable future of the Census and to proceed towards WP2 comprising the conceptual modelling of the Census data.

30 June 2021

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